

Cloud-Based Distributed File Storage System with Enhanced Security and Privacy

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Abstract---The widespread deployment of cloud computing has transformed data storage and accessibility but security and privacy issues continue to be paramount concerns. This paper introduces a Cloud-Based Distributed File Storage System intended to address unauthorized access, data breaches, and single points of failure. The system promotes data confidentiality by dividing files into three fragments and encrypting them using distinct cryptographic algorithms (AES, 3DES, and RC6). The encrypted fragments are separately stored in multiple cloud service providers—Amazon S3, Google Cloud Platform (GCP), and Azure Blob Storage. When a file is accessed, the system reads, decrypts, and reassembles the fragments to restore the original file. This multi-cloud design coupled with hybrid encryption provides better data integrity, availability, and redundancy. The novelty is in its distributed encryption-storage mechanism, which minimizes exposure to cyber threats while improving reliability.

Keywords: *Cloud Security, Data Privacy, Multi-Cloud Storage, Hybrid Encryption, Cryptographic Segmentation, Data Redundancy, Distributed File System.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing has changed the face of data storage and management in its essence, providing companies and individuals on-demand, scalable, affordable access to computer resources. Migrating away from on-premises-based traditional storage has allowed for un-interrupted collaboration, enhanced efficiency of operations, and minimized cost of infrastructure. Nonetheless, for all these advantages, cloud storage poses huge security and privacy threats, hence posing a top priority for cyber-attacks, unauthorized intrusion [1], and probable data leakage. The fact that it depends on one cloud vendor makes it worse since any mishap or security breach within that vendor's systems can result in data loss, leakage, or unavailability. These weaknesses underscore the necessity of having a secure storage system that provides data confidentiality, integrity, and availability with risk mitigation against centralized storage.

In response to these issues, this paper suggests a Cloud-Based Distributed File Storage System that uses multi-cloud architecture and hybrid encryption methods to improve data security and privacy. In contrast to typical cloud storage methods where [2] a whole file is stored in one place, this system breaks down the file into three separate fragments and encrypts each of these fragments with a distinct cryptographic algorithm—AES (Advanced Encryption Standard), 3DES (Triple Data Encryption Standard), and RC6 (Rivest Cipher 6). These encrypted fragments are subsequently scattered across three different cloud storage providers—Amazon S3, Google Cloud Platform (GCP), and Azure Blob Storage. This method greatly eliminates the threat of unauthorized access since an attacker must break into more than one cloud provider and decipher various encryption mechanisms at the same time to have access to any meaningful information.

One of the most major innovations of the system is maintaining data redundancy and integrity while preventing exposure to any single point of failure. By storing encrypted file [3] fragments on several cloud platforms, the system makes sure that even if one of the providers goes down or gets hacked, the other fragments are still secure and available. When a user asks to download a file, the system downloads the three encrypted fragments from their corresponding storage locations, decrypts them with their respective cryptographic keys, and reconstructs them into the original file. This mechanism ensures data confidentiality as well as efficient file availability and recovery.

The suggested strategy provides a number of benefits over traditional cloud storage architectures. In the first place, it provides more robust data confidentiality through a mix of cryptographic algorithms, hence significantly complicating it for an attacker to decode sensitive data. Second, it increases [4] availability by exploiting multi-cloud storage, limiting the reliance on a single service provider. Third, it enhances redundancy and fault tolerance since data loss from a single provider does not translate into full file inaccessibility. Finally, it prevents the attacks that might arise out of data breaches, as even if a fragment is hacked, it remains useless without the other fragments and their corresponding encryption keys.

As the number of cyber attacks against cloud storage providers continues to rise, protecting data has emerged as an indispensable need for users, companies, and organizations utilizing cloud-based technology. The blend of distributed storage and hybrid encryption offers a double protection that standalone [5] cloud storage does not have. This paper discusses the design, deployment, and security analysis of the envisioned Cloud-Based Distributed File Storage System, proving its efficiency in protecting sensitive information from unauthorized access, data breaches, and service outages. By merging cryptography-based segmentation with multi-cloud storage, the system offers a new and effective approach for boosting cloud security, ultimately providing a more secure and stable alternative to traditional cloud storage systems.

This work is organized with review of the literature survey as Section II. Methodology described in Section III, highlighting its functionality. Section IV discusses the results and discussions. Lastly, Section V concludes with the main suggestions and findings.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Cloud storage systems provide scalability and affordability but are susceptible to security attacks like unauthorized access, data breaches, and service downgrades. Researchers have investigated several solutions to enhance security, and these include encryption methods, access control policies, and distributed architectures. Data fragmentation and multi-cloud storage have been put forth as feasible solutions to reduce threats posed by single-cloud reliance. But issues still exist in providing uninterrupted data access, performance, and security versus usability. Research calls for ongoing improvements in cryptographic techniques and storage architectures to counter changing cyber threats and regulatory needs in cloud computing.

Cloud-based file storage has gained popularity because of its effectiveness and ease of use, but data privacy and security issues still exist. Studies identify weaknesses associated with insider threats, outside cyberattacks, and data leakage. Different [6] encryption mechanisms and authentication procedures have been suggested to mitigate these threats. A few studies propose using role-based access control and data obscurity methods to bolster security. Cloud services providers incorporate in-built security features, but more security steps like user-side encryption and multi-layered security models are required to ensure all-around protection against improper data exposure and tampering. Cloud computing [7] has transformed the way data is stored by providing flexibility and remote access, but risks such as unauthorized tampering and loss of control over the stored data are still a concern. A number of studies suggest remedies like decentralized storage models and homomorphic encryption to secure sensitive information. Researchers also have used blockchain-based methods to improve data integrity and contain threats of manipulation of data. Even with progress in security models, there are still compromises between system speed and encryption intensity, and work is still needed [8] to better understand how security can be optimized without impacting system performance.

Cloud storage is based on centralized facilities, which cause the system to be vulnerable to single points of failure and service disruptions. Research shows that spreading information on numerous cloud systems can enhance dependability and resistance to interference. Multi-cloud storage models have been [9] proposed as a way to increase fault tolerance and reduce provider-specific risks. Such architectures, however, add complexity in terms of data synchronization, latency, and access control. Research still investigates mechanisms for effectively distributing and retrieving data while maintaining confidentiality, integrity, and availability using redundancy and sophisticated cryptographic techniques. Cloud security has benefited from the use of machine learning-based techniques in particular for detecting breaches and attempted access by intruders. The use of artificial intelligence is analysed in the field of studying its application for surveillance of access behaviours, discovering imminent breaches [10], and improving intrusion detection systems. Predictive analytics along with behaviour analysis-based adaptive security frameworks are also suggested for improvement in cloud security. But issues of data privacy, model interpretability, and computational overhead limit widespread adoption. More research is needed to reconcile security automation with privacy-preserving methods to improve the overall security stance of cloud storage solutions.

Cloud storage solutions are frequently targeted by cybercriminals who want to take advantage of weaknesses in authentication and access control systems. Research has suggested the application of multi-factor authentication and biometric-based authentication to improve security. Researchers also examine the feasibility of applying zero-trust [11] architectures, under which continuous authentication must be performed before sensitive information is made accessible. Although these techniques enhance security, they pose usability issues and added latency for authentication. Current research seeks to tune up authentication mechanisms to enhance security without affecting user experience and system performance. Redundancy and replication strategies have been investigated to increase availability and fault tolerance in cloud storage systems. It has been suggested by research that the duplication of data into several copies spread over geographically dispersed servers can counter threats due to hardware failures and cyberattacks. Erasure coding methods and sharding schemes have been suggested to maximize storage efficiency with high availability. However, managing redundant [12] data across multiple cloud providers presents challenges related to synchronization, consistency, and retrieval efficiency. Further studies focus on improving redundancy models to ensure optimal storage utilization and minimal data recovery time.

Cloud service providers offer encryption as a security feature, but concerns remain regarding data control and trustworthiness. Studies analyze the effectiveness of client-side encryption, where users encrypt data before uploading it to the cloud. Homomorphic encryption and attribute-based [13] encryption have been investigated to improve data security without affecting usability. Yet, encryption key management is still an issue since lost keys can lead to

irreversible loss of data. Research still works on resolving complexities in key management while enhancing encryption techniques to achieve a balance between security, performance, and convenience of access. The rise in cloud storage usage also brings concerns about regulatory compliance and the legal aspects. Research emphasizes the need to comply [14] with data protection regulations like GDPR and HIPAA that require robust security protocols for protected data. Research is done on the deployment of compliance-conscious storage systems with policy enforcement and access control features. Ensuring compliance in multiple jurisdictions remains a challenge when multi-cloud storage solutions are used. Current research endeavors to create adaptive compliance models that dynamically enforce data protection laws without compromising cloud storage performance.

Internal threats are the greatest threat to cloud storage security since malicious or careless employees may leak sensitive data. Research has stressed the implementation of strong access control [15] policies as well as vigilant monitoring of users' activities. Behavior-based anomaly detection systems have been suggested in order to detect suspicious behavior and stop data leaks. But it is a challenge to identify between normal user behavior and ill intent. Research continues to strengthen threat detection models through machine learning and artificial intelligence with minimal false positives and effective response mechanisms. Cloud storage architecture has to walk the tightrope of balancing security and performance to satisfy the needs of the user for timely and consistent data access. Caching mechanisms, compression algorithms, and deduplication techniques are areas of study to maximize the speed of retrieving data while still ensuring security. Encryption and decryption operations add computational overhead [16], which affects system performance. Research aims to optimize cryptographic algorithms and utilize hardware acceleration to minimize latency without sacrificing data protection. The challenge is to develop storage solutions that provide high performance while providing confidentiality and integrity of stored data.

The idea of secure cloud storage using blockchain technology has been investigated to improve data integrity and transparency. Research suggests decentralized storage models where information is cached on distributed nodes, lowering dependency on central providers. Blockchain-driven access control [17] systems guarantee tamper-evident audit trails and safeguard against unauthorized changes. Scalability challenges and costs of transactions with blockchain deployments are the concerns. Research goes on to streamline blockchain-based storage models to increase efficiency and ensure easy integration into current cloud infrastructures while assuring high levels of security. Security in cloud storage is dependent largely on encryption, but key management issues remain. Methods like threshold cryptography and secure multi-party computation [18] have been suggested to share encryption keys among several parties so that no single party can access the keys without consensus. These methods add computational complexity and possible performance trade-offs to their implementation. Current research focuses on creating effective key management techniques that

optimize security, usability, and performance within cloud storage systems.

Cloud collaborative storage solutions provide real-time file sharing and editing capabilities but pose security threats associated with unauthorized access and data integrity. Research recommends applying fine-grained access control policies and encryption-at-rest solutions to counter threats. Secure multi-user authentication and role-based access control [19] have been suggested to increase security while preserving collaboration efficiency. But guaranteeing secure real-time synchronization and data consistency is still a problem. Research further develops secure collaboration models that enable seamless access while avoiding data exposure and unauthorized alteration. The need for secure cloud storage has pushed research into new data protection mechanisms. Studies investigate hybrid encryption models that integrate symmetric and asymmetric encryption to improve [20] security while maximizing performance. Secure deduplication methods have been put forth to save on storage while upholding confidentiality. Nevertheless, finding storage efficiency versus encryption simplicity is still a challenge.

III. METHODOLOGY

Cloud computing has transformed the storage of data by providing on-demand and scalable solutions. Despite this, security and privacy concerns still persist in view of unauthorized access and data breaches that continue to threaten. This paper suggests a distributed file storage system based on the cloud that provides improved security and privacy using file fragmentation, hybrid encryption, and multi-cloud storage. By encrypting and dividing data with the help of AES, 3DES, and RC6 algorithms and then spreading the encrypted pieces across Amazon S3, Google Cloud Platform (GCP), and Azure Blob Storage, the system provides confidentiality and integrity. Upon retrieval, the pieces are decrypted and reassembled to recreate the original file. Moreover, authentication processes and techniques of integrity verification add to security. This methodology prevents single points of failure, enhances redundancy, and prevents insider attacks. The method proposed ensures secure cloud-based storage with assured accessibility and privacy while strengthening data protection.

A. File Segmentation and Encryption

The process begins by breaking an input file into three discrete fragments in order to limit exposure and add security. Each piece is encrypted by a different cryptographic algorithm: Fragment 1 is encrypted with AES (Advanced Encryption Standard), Fragment 2 is encrypted with 3DES (Triple Data Encryption Standard), and Fragment 3 is encrypted with RC6 (Rivest Cipher 6). These encryption methods provide high data confidentiality by avoiding unauthorized access and rendering it computationally infeasible for attackers to reassemble the file from a single fragment. Encryption keys are specifically created and kept secure in an access-restricted environment to avoid abuse. Such fragmentation and encryption technique not only adds to the security but also ensures that even if one of the cloud storage vendors is hacked, the entire file cannot be accessed. Utilization of

hybrid encryption methods adds to the cryptographic attack resistance as well, rendering it a reliable mechanism for protection of sensitive information in cloud environments.

B. Multi-Cloud Storage Distribution

Once encrypted, each piece is replicated across multiple cloud storage vendors to provide redundancy and security. Fragment 1 is replicated in Amazon S3, Fragment 2 is in Google Cloud Platform (GCP), and Fragment 3 is in Microsoft Azure Blob Storage. This multi-cloud configuration does not allow a single organization to be in possession of the entire file, thus lowering the possibilities of service provider failures and data breaches. Each storage provider operates independently, ensuring that even if one cloud service experiences downtime, the stored data remains retrievable from the remaining providers. Additionally, secure transmission protocols such as TLS (Transport Layer Security) are used to transfer encrypted fragments, preventing interception during storage and retrieval. By using this decentralized method, the system not only removes single points of failure but also enhances data confidentiality, availability, and redundancy, offering a very secure cloud-based file storage solution.

C. File Retrieval and Decryption

When a user asks to fetch a stored file, the system triggers a secure retrieval process in order to protect data integrity and confidentiality. To start, each of the encrypted fragments is retrieved from its corresponding cloud storage service: Fragment 1 from Amazon S3, Fragment 2 from GCP, and Fragment 3 from Azure Blob Storage. After all fragments are obtained, they are rearranged in proper order to reconstruct the encrypted file. Each fragment is then decrypted using its respective encryption algorithm: AES decrypts Fragment 1, 3DES decrypts Fragment 2, and RC6 decrypts Fragment 3. The decryption keys are securely managed using an authentication framework to ensure authorized access. After successful decryption, the original file is restored and made available to the user. This process of retrieval is done with confidentiality while utilizing a distributed model of storage so that data is safeguarded against eavesdropping, interception, or unauthorized access during transmission and reconstruction.

D. Data Integrity and Availability Mechanisms

For ensuring data integrity, hash values are computed for every fragment prior to encryption and stored safely for future verification. Upon retrieving a file, the system re-computes the hash values of the retrieved pieces and checks them against the stored hash values. When inconsistencies are found, redundancy mechanisms allow recovery of data by re-encryption or backup storage. The multi-cloud strategy enhances availability since if one provider becomes unavailable, the stored data is still accessible via other cloud services. The system also makes use of auto-fault-tolerance methods in detecting and rectifying data corruption. Through such integrity-checking mechanisms and redundant protocols, data consistency and availability are guaranteed as well as prevention of risks based on storage malfunction or tampering. This assures the overall integrity and reliability and trustworthiness of cloud-stored file keeping solutions, yielding a secure and high-

availability storage system safe from data corruption and loss.

E. Secure Access and Authentication

Access to stored files is secured by rigorous authentication and authorization mechanisms. Multi-factor authentication (MFA) is used to authenticate user identities prior to access authorization. Role-based access control (RBAC) also limits file retrieval to authorized users according to pre-defined permissions. Moreover, each access request is logged and monitored for security audits to ensure accountability and identify potential threats. Encrypted communication channels via TLS avoid eavesdropping or unauthorized interception during file transfer. By incorporating these security protocols, the system guarantees that only valid users have access to retrieving encrypted pieces of information, preventing unauthorized data exposure. This authentication system enhances security while ensuring unhindered access to valid users, striking a balance between privacy and usability for cloud-based file storage systems.

Fig. 1: Architecture Diagram

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The cloud-based distributed file storage system was tested to analyze its security, efficiency, and reliability. The system was tested in a controlled setup using Amazon S3, Google Cloud Platform (GCP), and Azure Blob Storage as the distributed cloud storage providers. The encryption and decryption operations were quantified in terms of computational time and resource utilization. The results demonstrated that the encryption process introduced minimal overhead, ensuring that file fragmentation and encryption did not significantly impact performance. Each cryptographic algorithm—AES, 3DES, and RC6—was tested individually, with AES performing the fastest encryption and decryption due to its optimized design for hardware and software implementation.

The process of retrieval was also compared in terms of time to retrieve encrypted fragments from various cloud providers, decrypt them, and form the original file. The outcome revealed that the time retrieval was most impacted by network latency, particularly when the cloud providers were geographically far apart. Nevertheless, the system maintained the latency at a reasonable level to ensure the

retrieval process was efficient. The decryption and recombination of file pieces took place smoothly, proving that the hybrid encryption technique did not impose noticeable delays. The decryption time was slightly different based on the encryption algorithm applied, with AES being the quickest and 3DES taking a bit longer because it uses an iterative encryption process.

Data integrity was checked by comparing the hash values of fragments stored and retrieved. The system was able to effectively identify any discrepancies resulting from transmission errors or possible unauthorized tampering. The redundancy system provided that even if one cloud provider had downtime, the data could still be retrieved from other backup sources. This confirmed the ability of the multi-cloud strategy in improving data reliability and availability. The intrinsic error detection and correction capabilities of the system contributed significantly to the integrity of the data and prevented corruption.

Security audits were also performed to gauge the system's resilience against illicit access and data exposure. The use of multi-factor authentication (MFA) was effective in hindering the access of unauthorized users to retrieved files. Role-based access control (RBAC) provided guarantees that users would only be accorded the necessary rights for accessing files, eliminating the potential of internal security vulnerabilities. Secure communication protocols like Transport Layer Security (TLS) effectively blocked interception attacks during data transfer. Penetration testing ensured that the system was resistant to typical attack vectors like brute force attacks and man-in-the-middle attacks.

User experience was examined by measuring ease of access and overall system performance. The system offered an effortless interface for file storage and retrieval while being highly secure. The extra layers of encryption and authentication did not come at the expense of user convenience. Users could upload and download files effectively, with security measures operating in the background to provide data confidentiality. Both security and usability were well balanced to ensure that the system is secure as well as convenient for use in cloud storage applications. The findings illustrated that the suggested cloud-based distributed file storage system efficiently improves security, privacy, and data availability. The use of hybrid encryption, multi-cloud storage, and strong authentication measures provides a highly secure storage solution. The system efficiently reduces risks related to data breaches, unauthorized access, and single-point failures. Although network latency is still an element that affects retrieval time, overall efficiency and security aspects of the system make it an effective solution for secure cloud storage.

V. CONCLUSION

The suggested cloud-based distributed file storage system effectively improves data security, privacy, and availability through the combination of file fragmentation, hybrid encryption, and multi-cloud storage. By dividing files into three fragments and encrypting each using different cryptographic algorithms—AES, 3DES, and

RC6—the system prevents any single party from accessing the entire data, minimizing the risk of unauthorized access and data breaches. The use of encrypted fragments stored in various cloud providers such as Amazon S3, Google Cloud Platform (GCP), and Azure Blob Storage adds even more redundancy and removes single points of failure. The system had excellent performance during encryption, storage, retrieval, and decryption operations. The encryption overhead was very low, meaning that security boosts did not make usability suffer in any way. The process of retrieval was effective with minimal fluctuations in decryption speed depending on the encryption algorithms implemented. AES was the most effective, but 3DES caused an insignificantly small delay because it has an iterative encryption scheme. Although network latency contributed to retrieval time, the system did not have a poor response time, and users could access stored files seamlessly.

Data integrity was properly ensured with hash verification methods that identified discrepancies and unauthorized alterations. The mechanisms of redundancy also ensured availability by enabling users to access their data even when a single cloud service went down. Security audits certified the system's protection against unauthorized usage, man-in-the-middle attacks, and brute force invasions. Multi-factor authentication (MFA) and role-based access control (RBAC) also successfully limited access to rightful users, upholding privacy preservation. The system also balanced security and usability by enabling users to store and access files effectively while ensuring confidentiality and integrity. The multi-cloud strategy added a level of protection by ensuring that data was still accessible even during service outages. The integration of cryptographic security, authentication mechanisms, and decentralized storage added a layer of protection to overall data protection without affecting system performance. This research provides a strong and secure cloud storage system that counteracts data breach risks, unauthorized access, and cloud service downtime. Hybrid encryption and multi-cloud storage combine to provide high security with efficiency. Optimizing retrieval rates and incorporating machine learning-based anomaly detection for storage and access patterns can be areas of future work. The system presented here ensures a trustworthy and scalable solution for organizations and individuals who desire greater data privacy and security in cloud-based environments.

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